

ANALYSIS AND OPTIMAL DESIGN OF DAMPING PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

R.Rikards, A.Chate

Department of Strength of Materials, Riga Technical University
1 Kalku St., LV1047, Riga , LATVIA

ABSTRACT

The present investigation concerned with the predicting of damping properties by finite element method (FEM) of anisotropic fibre-reinforced composite laminated plates. The finite element used for analysis of problem is triangular finite element, based on first order shear deformation theory of plates. Damping properties of structure are characterized by specific damping capacity (SDC) for each natural frequency. Optimal design problems of composite plates are solved with new approach, based on planning of experiments, computer simulation by FEM, determination of simple mathematical models for optimal design and, finally, optimization by random search method. Examples of optimal design of laminated composite plates are considered.

Keywords: laminated composite, plates, finite element method, vibration, damping, optimal design.

1. INTRODUCTION

Methods of reliable prediction of the dynamic properties of transverse vibration of the composite plates have received much attention. Adams and Bacon [1], Ni *et al.* [2] and Malhorta *et al.* [3] used the classical plate theory (CPT) for the damping analysis of laminated plates. Lin *et al.*[4], Bicos and Springer [5] , Alam and Asnani [6] introduced Mindlin (Timoshenko) first order shear deformation theory (FOSDT) for damping analysis of composite plates.

The dynamic properties of composite plate are characterized by natural frequencies and corresponding modal loss factor η for each frequency. Specific damping capacity (SDC) is defined as

$$\psi = \frac{\Delta U}{U_{\max}} = 2\pi\eta, \quad (1)$$

where ΔU is the strain energy dissipated during one cycle of vibration, U_{\max} is total strain energy of the entire laminated plate at maximum of displacement during the same cycle.

In the present investigation we have analysed the natural frequencies and SDC of laminated composite plates using finite element model , based on FOSDT, described in Ref. [7] and damped

element model presented in Ref. [1].

Optimal design of damping properties of laminated composite plates is based on new approach (see Ref.[8]). Optimal design problem is divided into the following stages : chose of design parameters and establishment of the domain of search, elaboration of plans of experiment, performing the experiments (determination the natural frequencies and SDC of plate) by computer simulation (FEM analysis) in chosen number of points in the domain of search, determination of simple mathematical models from the data of experiments, optimization by the method of nonlinear programming on the basis of simple mathematical models of plate and, finally, verification experiments (FEM analysis) at the point of optimum.

2. THEORY

2.1. Strain energy of laminate

In Mindlin (Timoshenko) plate the displacements can be expressed as (see Ref. [9])

$$u = u_0 + \gamma_x z; \quad v = v_0 + \gamma_y z; \quad w = w_0, \quad (2)$$

where u, v, w are the displacements in the directions of reference axes x, y, z respectively (see Fig.1), u_0, v_0, w_0 are the displacements at the reference plane, and γ_x, γ_y are rotations, connected with transverse shear deformations.

Let us consider a single lamina with reference axis 1, 2, 3. If suffix 1 denotes the fibre direction and 2, 3 are the two directions transverse to that of the fibre then constitutive relations for any layer of orthotropic material are

$$\sigma_* = C_L \varepsilon_* \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_*^T = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6\}$, $\varepsilon_*^T = \{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_4, \varepsilon_5, \varepsilon_6\}$, and C_L is well known stiffness matrix of lamina with plane stress reduced stiffness components including transverse shear stiffness, which are referred to material properties

$$E_1; E_2 = E_3; G_{13} = G_{12}; G_{23}; \nu_{13} = \nu_{12}; \nu_{23} \quad (4)$$

Transforming the strains with respect to fiber orientation ε_* to the strains ε in the direction of the laminated plate axis $x, y,$ and z , we have

$$\varepsilon_* = T \varepsilon, \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. Multilayered composite plate with uni directional fibre-reinforced layers.

where T is transformation matrix and

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T = \{\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_z, \gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{xy}\}, \quad (6)$$

The strain energy U_L of each layer is

$$U_L = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_L} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_*^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_* dV_L, \quad (7)$$

where V_L is the volume of each layer. Substituting equations (3) and (5) into functional (7), we have

$$U_L = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_L} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \mathbf{A}_L \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dV_L, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_L = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{C}_L \mathbf{T}_T \quad (9)$$

Thus, the total strain energy of laminate is

$$U = \sum_{L=1}^K U_L, \quad (10)$$

where K is the number of layers.

2.2. Dissipated energy

According Adams and Bacon [4], if an element consisting of the L - th layer, of unit width, of unit length and distance z from reference plane, is considered, the energy dissipated in the element can be separated into five components

$$\delta(\Delta U) = \sum \delta(\Delta U_i); \quad i=1,2,4,5,6, \quad (11)$$

where ΔU_i is the energy dissipated by σ_i^* during deformation of element. The specific damping capacity (SDC) ψ is defined by formula (1) and thus $\delta(\Delta U_i)$ can be expressed as

$$\delta(\Delta U) = \frac{1}{2} \psi_i^* \sigma_i^* \varepsilon_i; \quad i=1,2,4,5,6, \quad (12)$$

where ψ_i are the SDC of the corresponding unidirectional reinforced layer. Thus the total energy dissipated in the L-th layer can be expressed as

$$\Delta U_L = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_L} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_*^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}_L \boldsymbol{\sigma}_* dV_L, \quad (13)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_i = \text{diag } \psi_i; \quad i=1,2,4,5,6, \quad (14)$$

Substituting expressions (3) and (5) into (13) ΔU_L can be written as

$$\Delta U_L = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_L} \varepsilon^T A_L^D \varepsilon dV_L, \quad (15)$$

where damping matrix A_L^D is

$$A_L^D = T^T \psi_L C_L T \quad (16)$$

Thus the total dissipated energy of laminate from K layers is

$$\Delta U = \sum_{L=1}^K \Delta U_L \quad (17)$$

2.3. Finite element modelling

The finite element used for analysis of problem is the six node triangular finite element with five degrees of freedom in each node (3 displacements and 2 rotations). The stiffness K_e and mass M_e matrices of the finite element being defined in details in Ref. [7]. Here this finite element we have used with some improvements. At the first shear correction factors k_4^2 and k_5^2 is introduced to account the fact that transverse shear strain distribution is not uniform through the plate stiffness. The second, selective integration procedure for the stiffness matrix is developed. It allows to analyse both thick and thin plates. Using expression (17) in the same manner as stiffness matrix K_e the damped stiffness matrix H_e was obtained.

$$\Delta U_L = \frac{1}{2} \delta_e^T H_e \delta_e, \quad (18)$$

where δ_e is the vector of displacement parameters of finite element. It should be noted that damped stiffness matrix is an ansymmetric matrix.

2.4. Equation of motion

For linear viscoelastic materials an energy dissipation in harmonic vibrations is taken into account by complex modulus of elasticity A_{ijkl}^*

$$A_{ijkl}^* = A_{ijkl} (1 + i \eta_{(ijkl)}); \quad i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3 \quad (19)$$

where $\eta_{(ijkl)}$ is material loss factors and A_{ijkl} is components of elastic stiffness tensor of material. For this model of composite material equation of motion for free vibrations is

$$M u_* + K_* u_* = 0, \quad (20)$$

where u_* is complex displacements, M is real mass matrix, K_* is complex stiffness matrix with real K' and imaginary K'' parts

$$K_* = K' + i K'' \quad (21)$$

Using $u_* = u_*^\circ = e^{i\omega_* t}$, for free vibrations we have

$$K_* u_*^\circ = \lambda_* M u_*^\circ, \quad (22)$$

where $\lambda_* = \omega_*^2$ is a complex eigenvalue, ω_* is a complex frequency, u_*° is a complex eigenvector. Exact

damped frequencies and damped vibration modes can be determined from equation (22) by Lanczos method (see for example Ref. [9]) or by other methods.

More simplified approach is to solve eigenvalue problem for elastic vibrations using only real part of stiffness matrix

$$K'u_0 = \lambda Mu_0 \quad (23)$$

To determine elastic frequencies and elastic vibration modes from equation (23) we use subspace iteration method. Using expressions (1), (10) and (18) for all structure it is possible to calculate modal loss factors for each vibration mode.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The model, the algorithm and the computer code developed during present study was effected by comparing the results of the present method to existing numerical and experimental results. The plates are in fact all of square planform of side length a , described by a symbolism defining the boundary conditions at their four edges : a SCSF, for instance, means a plate whose edges are simply supported, clamped, simply supported and free respectively, starting from the edge $x=0$ and proceeding clockwise around the plate.

3.1. Example 1

Let us consider the laminate composite square plate made from glass fibre - rein forced plastic (see Ref.[4]). The parameters of unidirectional glass fibre - reinforced lamina are:

Figure 2. Natural frequency ω and specific damping capacity (SDC) for square plate with FFFF (a) and FCFC (b) boundary conditions.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_1 &= 37.78 \text{ GPa}; & E_2 = E_3 &= 10.9 \text{ GPa}; & G_{23} = G_{12} = G_{13} &= 4.91 \text{ GPa}; \\
\psi_1 &= 87\%; & \psi_2 &= 5.05\%; & \psi_{23} = \psi_{12} = \psi_{13} &= 6.91\%; \\
\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} &= 0.3; & \rho &= 1813.9 \text{ kg/m}^3 & &
\end{aligned}
\tag{24}$$

Here values of specific damping capacity (SDC) ψ_i are given in per cent ($\psi_i \% = \psi_i * 100\%$). Thickness of layer is $h_L = 0.0002562\text{m}$. We consider 8 layer plate with stacking sequence of layers ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$)s. Thickness of plate is $h=0.00205 \text{ m}$ and side length of plate is $a=0.227 \text{ m}$. For this stacking sequence of layers calculated shear correction factors are $k_4^2=0.840$ and $k_5^2=0.777$. Plate have the FFFF boundary conditions. In Table 1 are shown the first six natural frequencies and corresponding specific damping capacity (SDC) calculated by present theory in comparison with theoretical prediction and experimental results by Lin et al. (see Ref [4]). Here also are shown present results for different number of finite elements (NE).

Table 1. Natural frequencies f and specific damping capacity (SDC) for six first vibration modes of 8 layer square plate

No.	Parameters	Present theory				Theory [4]	Exper. [4]
		NE=32	NE=72	NE=200	NE=338		
1.	f(Hz)	66.7	68.6	69.1	68.9	66.4	62.2
	SDC(%)	6.96	6.80	6.72	6.71	7.16	6.70
2.	f(Hz)	124.5	128.9	131.4	131.82	131.62	131.4
	SDC(%)	2.55	2.57	2.58	2.59	2.47	2.80
3.	f(Hz)	157.8	162.8	165.6	166.1	164.5	159.2
	SDC(%)	1.78	1.74	1.72	1.70	1.62	1.90
4.	f(Hz)	207.5	204.8	196.2	192.7	189.8	180.5
	SDC(%)	4.23	4.55	4.89	4.85	4.87	4.90
5.	f(Hz)	338.3	242.8	218.4	214.8	208.9	200.1
	SDC(%)	5.99	4.76	3.79	3.70	3.73	3.20
6.	f(Hz)	361.4	363.0	367.3	354.9	347.2	326.7
	SDC(%)	3.02	2.91	2.88	5.04	5.09	5.80

3.2. Example 2

Let us consider the square plate with the same lamina properties (24) as in pervious example. The objective is to design plate with predicted dynamic and damping properties. The 8 layer plate is with symmetric ($\beta, -\beta, \beta, -\beta$)s laminate configuration shown in Figure 1. We examine two plates with different boundary conditions : FFFF (all edges of plate are free) and FCFC (two edges of plate are free and two - clamped). The specific damping capacity (SDC) and natural frequencies as function of the ply fibre orientation angle β with respect to x direction of plate are shown in Figure 2.

For FFFF boundary conditions (see Figure 2a) there are presented the first natural frequency ω_1 (rad/s) and corresponding specific damping capacity SDC_1 (%). For FCFC boundary conditions (see Figure 2b) there are presented two first frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 and corresponding SDC_1 and SDC_2 as function of ply fiber orientation angle β . We see that for both frequencies of FCFC plate maximum in frequency curves corresponds to minimum in SDC curves. So the frequency and damping characteristic of plate are contradictory. In this case it is necessary to formulate the optimal design problem.

3.2. Example 3.

Let us consider the optimal design problem for the same square plate ($a=0.227m$, $h_L=0.0002562m$) as in example 2 with the same lamina properties (24) and with FCFC boundary conditions. To solve optimal design problem new approach based on planning of experiments [8] is used. The design parameters are : ply angle $x_1=\beta$ and number of layers $x_2=K$. We define the domain of search for the design parameters by following constraints.

$$0 \leq x_1 \leq 90; \quad 4 \leq x_2 \leq 68 \quad (25)$$

In this domain of search plan of experiment with 31 points [8] was used. In these points using FEM natural frequencies and specific damping capacity were calculated. Using these data of experiment program RESINT [8] gives the following simple mathematical model for the first frequency ω_1 of the plate

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1(x) &= -3075 + 1001 z_1^{-1} + 5052 z_1 z_2 + 800.6 z_1^{-1} z_2 ; \\ z_1 &= 0.5 + 0.0111 x_1; \quad z_2 = 0.3667 + 0.01667 x_2 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Also from the data of experiment with program RESINT [8] a simple mathematical model for the corresponding specific damping capacity SDC_1 was obtained

$$SDC_1(x) = 92.46 - 62.06 z_1 - 35.92 z_1^{-1} + 7.391 z_1^3 + 0.5762 z_1 z_2^2 + 1.904 z_1^{-3} - 0.2069 z_2^3 \quad (27)$$

Here for z_i we have the same expressions as for function (26).

The objective function is weight or mass of the plate. Optimization problem is to minimize the mass m of plate

$$m(x) = \rho a^2 h_L x_2 \Rightarrow \min \quad (28)$$

under constraints on the domain of search (25) and constraints on the first natural frequency and corresponding SDC

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1(x) &\geq \omega_* \\ SDC(x) &\geq SDC_* \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Here ω_* , SDC_* are predicted frequency and loss factor of the plate. For $\omega_*=2500$ rad/s and $SDC_*=4.5\%$ program SUPLEX [8] gives the following optimal solution x_* of this problem : $x_1^*=40^\circ$; $x_2^*=26$ layers; $m(x_*)=0,6248$ kg.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Damping properties of multilayered composite plate for vibration analysis are taken into account by complex modulus of elasticity. Specific damping capacity (SDC) of laminated plates for each of vibration mode is calculated by energy approach. Strain energy dissipated per one cycle of vibration is calculated using elastic vibration modes. Numerical examples for frequency and damping analysis shows good agreement with published theoretical and experimental results. An example of minimum mass design of laminated composite plate with frequency and damping constraints is discussed.

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